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THE MAIN FEATURES OF INTELLIGENT TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

In the context of Global changes, the economy of our country today is the digital economy that motivates the development and the one that is associated with it how many effective technologies are rapidly entering our lives.

Key words: modern technologies, economy, IT developments, e-version developments, internet.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of Global changes, the economy of our country today is the digital economy that motivates the development and the one that is associated with it how many effective technologies are rapidly entering our lives. In the context of global globalization, foreign migration, international trade and capital movement, tourism, foreign investment, especially IT development affects the economic growth rates of countries.

Informational a World-Wide Developer of innovations for content creation YouTube, Facebook, Google, Wikipedia, Wikileaks, Amazon, Alibaba and more new progressive information by a number of global companies with technology, business issues as well as commercial problems are solved and they say that every new generation of information Systems is a bunch of new innovations they are the reason for the emergence and further development of services. By digital economy, only blockchain (Blockchain issues of technology and their use in international financial markets or it is not necessary to understand cryptocurrencies. World Bank “Digital conclusions of his study” dividends " in the development of the economy of countries shows how relevant and important the digital economy is.

METHODS

There are different platforms for different forms of the digital shadow economy. There is a physical black market that exists for the sale of illegal goods and services, as well as a fraudulent data market in which actors exchange stolen data and private information. The physical marketplace functions thanks to special platforms that allow actors to remain anonymous. The fraudulent data market operates on the basis of conventional Internet sites. Various economic actors can act as actors in the digital shadow economy: sellers and service providers, consumers, individuals and legal entities, multinational companies, and commercial networks. One of the main economic drivers of participation in the digital shadow economy is the presence of clear economic benefits. These are a variety of available goods and services, easy and convenient access to a large amount of information about goods, the ability to communicate with the seller, a large number of promotions, the availability of conditions for the return of goods, convenient payment terms. Participants are also stimulated by the difference in price between goods in online stores and in traditional stores. The financial position of the actor is of great importance. According to some studies, subjects that are more financially independent are less likely to become participants in the digital shadow economy. The digital shadow economy is a reality today. Any economic agents can become actors of the digital shadow economy. To operate in the digital shadow economy, various special platforms are used, which are currently forming a fullfledged shadow digital ecosystem, the task of which is to ensure the anonymity of participants and create obstacles for government bodies. Measuring the volume of the digital shadow economy using classical methods for assessing the shadow economy is difficult due to the fact that they do not reflect the characteristics of the phenomenon under study. Based on the theoretical substantiation of the digital shadow economy, for an indirect assessment of development trends, an assessment can be carried out in the context of three directions: assessment of the level of dissemination of digital technologies, assessment of the population's incentives to participate in the shadow economy, assessment of barriers to the development of the digital shadow economy.

RESULTS

In particular, a 10 percent increase in the speed of the internet led to an increase in the country's GDP comes. If in developed countries this figure is 1.21 percent, 1.38% in developing countries. So internet speed 2 if the rate increases, a 13-14 percent increase in the volume of GDP can be achieved. For example, the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan in 2020 total for state programs 18.2 trl.so ‘ m and 10.3 billion dollar spending is in sight caught. Modern scientific approaches and innovations

in the digital economy it will be important and priority. The scientific capacity is high in this which networks prosper.

The volume of GDP in the developed countries of the digital economy is also, The share of GDP per capita is also high. In this respect, our state one goal is for the leader to focus heavily on the issue, which is also if, firstly, to raise the standard of living of the population, and secondly, to increase the real income of the population and please our people. It is for this reason that the development of the state and society is further in order to accelerate, the leadership of the Republic made several important decisions accepted. For example, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 28, 2018 The most important mentor for 2019 to the Supreme Assembly on tasks In his address, too, on the development of the digital economy in our country he mentioned: "digital technologies of all sectors of the economy the "National concept of the digital economy", which will be updated on the basis of we need to work out. On this basis, the program "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" we need to live. The digital economy has a gross domestic product of at least. Growing by 30 percent allows you to sharply reduce corruption. Prestigious analysis by international organizations is also confirming this. Therefore The "road " to the government on the transition to the digital economy in two months the development of the " map " will be commissioned. To ensure information security in this regard special attention is needed". In connection with this appeal to say that it is possible that the post-industrial or information services sector to the community of the country it includes countries that make up more than 60% of their gross national income. This financing software development networks in states the amount increased more than 130 times in the next thirty years. The penetration of new technologies into our country in all areas leading to the transition of Public Administration and economy to electronic appearance coming.

DISCUSSION

While, to which our country has increased the volume of foreign trade an example is. The result is a new state and non-state electronic service types appeared, new markets were formed and traditional business models the transformation into an electronic form began. Openness as a result of the reforms carried out in the new Uzbekistan, the development of international economic and political relations makes industrial sectors in our country modernization, technical and technological re-equipment created its capabilities. "E-Government", " e-governance", Many phrases like "telecommunications", "Internet", " website it has become an integral part of our life. Dog all of our daily lives covering the field. It is known that today the digital economy is in the creation of added value also gaining importance. Various algorithms, processes and numerical information is the main determinant in the strategic development of corporate business gaining power. Digital nonlinear factors of banks it

is defining its competitiveness, affecting its effectiveness. Experts believe that as of 2020, about 30 of the largest banks more than a percentage of their work activities from blockchain technology began to use. This is due to the fact that the blockchain technology is relatively despite the fact that it has just been created, its revolutionary in existing business processes huge interest among financial market participants, whose coverage of changes the reason for the awakening can be shown.

A decline in real disposable income and an increase in the proportion of the population with incomes below the subsistence level creates risks of involving a large number of people in the operations of the digital shadow economy. A dramatic reduction in costs through the use of information technology, in the absence of institutional control, can attract businesses to the digital shadow economy. The digital shadow economy creates additional sources of inflationary pressure, complicates the restructuring of the economy, and generates inadequate signals to business. Financial electronic fraud hinders the implementation of an effective social policy of the state, reducing the collection of taxes in the state budget, restricting the possibilities of state regulation, and serves as a factor in the deterioration of the investment climate in the country. The digital shadow economy 415 complicates the configuration of the pension, insurance and medical systems, thereby violating the social contract between citizens and the state (the exchange of taxes for public goods). The main barriers to the growth of the digital shadow economy are a high level of cyber security, which provides protection against hacker attacks, and a system for protecting intellectual property rights, which prevents the development of Internet piracy.

As a result-dirty money laundering, embezzlement of funds, inefficient and aimless spending, increase either there is no way to hide and show. Which is legal funds to the economy increases the flow, taxes are paid on time and correctly, the budget distribution is open will, funds directed to the social sphere will not be stolen, schools, hospitals, the money allocated to the roads will be fully reached, electron commercial, internet banking, electronic security, internet advertising and so on, Internet games are seen. The growth of the digital economy is beyond what we have listed above to increase labor efficiency in production, companies increase in competitiveness, decrease in production costs, to the creation of new jobs, the emergence of new modern professions, overcoming poverty and losing social inequality without much influence will not remain.

CONCLUSION

One of the important challenges of digital asset management is is their legal protection. It should be noted that in short periods and from the original creating a copy of digital assets at a lower cost as well as launching can. This, of course, affects the total income of digital assets. The use of cloud technology in managing digital assets

is key information protection in terms of technical, legal and organizational is the development of methods on. Imagine the development of digital assets without the development of digital commerce it's hard to do. Digital commerce, on the other hand, offers simple and reliable digital payment systems requires creation. When servicing the first" online " payment systems from credit and debit cards due to the prevalence among the population used. Credit card issuers" Visa "and" Master Card " from sellers demand the conditions for the implementation of high security measures in the exchange of information they were. The study of the latest trends in the world is unprofitable will not. Because in the world, material and intangible assets in the balance sheet in the period of rapid replacement of its place, we also focus only on the products not focusing on exports, but know-how, blockchain technology activities Broad from the possibilities of the digital economy, studying in harmony with the Times it is desirable that we take the use to a new level compute. In conclusion, it can be said that blockchain technology, cryptocurrencies are also a branch of the digital economy. But digital economy by definition, digital communications, an economy carried out with the help of IT is understood. In this, also as a means of ending the hidden economy can look. Because first of all, all transactions are registered electronically the transition is achieved, and the second is transparent. In addition, in production cost of products and services due to the application of new IT technologies declines.

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